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AN ENGINEERING CURRICULUM OR A CURRICULUM TO SHAPE ENGINEERS?

N. van Hattum-Janssen

Saxion University of Applied Sciences, the Netherlands

M. Endedijk

University of Twente, the Netherlands

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How do we attract more students to engineering education and how do we keep them in the engineering field after their graduation? What makes them stay in engineering? In the project Mind the Gap we found that their professional identity is a key concept to understand the study and career choices they make. In the project Bridge the Gap, a continuation of Mind the Gap, we explore the development of professional identity over time and the contextual factors that influence the development of professional identity. Research on the formation of professional identity acknowledges a role of the educational context but is not explicit on how this process takes place (Trede, Macklin, & Bridges, 2012; Morelock, 2017). Abrandt Dahlgren et al. (2006) argue that professional learning contexts help students to identify the boundaries of their own professional context and to sharpen their professional identity. Through the contact of students with those from other disciplinary areas, for example in multi-disciplinary projects, students become more aware of their own identity as a professional from a specific field. Engineering curricula provide, to a greater or a lesser extent, experiences that shape the professional identity of a student. This workshop aimed to get a clear(er) picture of how curricula can influence professional identity and how a more focused approach to curriculum development can contribute to a stronger focus on the professional identity of engineering students, preparing them, as such, better for well-considered choices for study and career.

A framework was presented to analyse professional socialisation and the degree to which socialising experiences are provided in the curriculum. The framework consists of two dimensions: curriculum components and engagement levels. The curriculum components are based on Thijs and van den Akker (2009). The engagement levels are based on the levels of Weidman, Twale and Stein (2001). Their research starts from the experiences of the individual student and delineates the stages of development of professional identity that an individual goes through. The framework presented here uses these in order to establish the kind of experiences a curriculum needs to provide for a student that enable this development. The experiences stimulate transitions from early stage professional development, where role acquisition is starting, till a personalized stage, where the professional role is internalised and fused with personal and social roles.

The framework as presented was used to categorise the nature of the socialising experiences from less to more engagement of the individual student with the formation of his or her own professional identity, ranging from knowledge about, exposure to, interaction with to reflection on the (possible) professional context. The course rationale, learning goals of modules, teaching and learning methods and assessment methods were taken into account in this categorisation process, which left other relevant curriculum components like grouping, the role of the teacher, and time were left out of scope for the moment. Table 1 shows the framework for the analysis of experiences of professional socialisation.

Table 1. Framework for the analysis of experiences of professional socialisation in engineering curricula

Curriculum component	Level of engagement			
	Knowledge acquisition	Exposure	Interaction	Reflection
Rationale				
Aims & objectives				
Teaching & learning				
Assessment				
Teacher role*				
Role of professional*				
Facilities and resources*				
Grouping*				
Location*				
Time*				

*Not taken into account in the workshop

More than 30 participants used this trial version of the framework in the workshop. Before completing the form that was handed out, the participants went back to their personal professional socialisation process by identifying experiences that significantly contributed to their professional identity as an engineer or as another type of professional they most identify with. These experiences could be related to their degree programme or to their professional life after graduation. A number of different experiences were mentioned; company visits, study trips and internships, as well as specific events related to the first job after graduation. Participants then listed a number of possible socialising experiences in the curricula of their engineering degree

programmes that may contribute to the professional identity of their students. The participants identified socialising experiences like excursions, graduation projects, internships in different professional contexts, a flexible curriculum, reflection, events to meet young professionals and the creation of start-ups by students. In order to better understand the impact of these experiences the participants used the framework to identify the nature of the experiences by placing the experiences in the framework as shown in Table 1.

The results of the participants show that the rationale of the programmes is mostly not mentioned by the participants. Socialising experiences are mentioned, but not directly related to the rationale of the degree programme. They did not refer to the inclusion of professional socialisation in the competencies of the programme or in general in documents on the programme outline. According to the participants, the learning goals of modules do sometimes refer to professional socialisation. Teaching and learning methods and assessment method were most frequently mentioned. The level of involvement of the students was often exposure or interaction. Knowledge on the professional field without exposure was specifically mentioned by two groups that referred to modules on engineering skills. In these modules, students are not yet exposed to the professional practice, but simulate it at their university. Reflection and the role of professionals in reflection was connected to assessment activities by several groups.

The findings of the groups were compared with the preliminary findings of the analysis of two comparable engineering curricula, one at a university and one at a university of applied sciences. Two degree programme documents and 38 module descriptions were analysed with Atlas.ti. Fragments that refer to professional socialisation were related, if applicable, to the curriculum components rationale, learning goals, teaching and learning methods, materials and resources, grouping and assessment. The remaining curriculum components will be explored by interviews. The fragments were then categorised as knowledge acquisition, exposure, interaction or reflection. The analysis showed that experiences of professional socialisation are clearly present in rationale and learning goals, as opposed to what the participants stated, but far less in teaching and learning methods and assessment. Furthermore, experiences aimed at reflection on professional socialisation at these institutions of higher education were not necessarily preceded by exposure or interaction, making the reflection on their professional socialisation a somewhat theoretical exercise for students.

Conclusions

The framework in its current version is a first step towards a more systematic curriculum analysis for experiences of professional socialisation of engineering curricula. By making a comprehensive overview of the curriculum and distinguishing levels of engagement in experiences of professional socialisation, the degree to which a curriculum potentially contributes to professional identity development can be explored. The analysis that was carried out in the workshop was based on important

experiences as identified by the participant and revealed an incomplete coverage of the framework, focussing mainly on exposure and interaction as far as the levels of engagement are concerned and on teaching and learning methods and assessment as far as the curriculum components are concerned. The framework is expected to be helpful in curriculum design when aiming for more explicit attention for the professional identity of engineering students and the role of experiences of professional socialisation.

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